

PATTERNS OF NICOTINE USE AMONG ADULT PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND ASSOCIATION WITH ITS SEVERITY

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Abstract

Purpose: Chronic respiratory disease (CRD) is a major global health issue, especially in India. CRD includes asthma and COPD, impacting around 100 million people in India. Prevalence rates vary widely from 2% to 22% in men and from 1.2% to 19% in women across studies. These differences in prevalence demonstrate the diverse impact of CRD influenced by various factors like demographics, environment, and lifestyle. **Methodology:** This is cross sectional observational study conducted among the patients diagnosed with COPD, attending the Respiratory Medicine outpatient department, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital & Research Centre within the study period of 6 months. The total sample size of the study was 200 participants. The collected data was entered in Microsoft Excel. Coding of the variables was done. Analysis was done using SPSS software (Version 27, IBM). **Findings:** Participants aged 35-40 years are 14%, 41-50 years are 28%, 51-60 years are 34%, and over 60 years are 24%. The gender distribution is 75% male and 25% female. Nicotine use patterns vary among participants - beedis at 37.5%, chewing tobacco at 25%, cigarettes at 23.5%, betel quid with tobacco at 11.5%, and gutka at 2.5%. Fagerstrom Test shows different addiction levels: low dependence - 27, low to moderate - 68, moderate - 66, high - 39. Nicotine use and COPD presence are significantly related (p-value 0.000), with 75% of users having COPD. Among users, 25% do not have COPD, while among non-users, 75% are COPD-free. **Conclusions:** This research emphasizes the notable impact of nicotine consumption in COPD patients and its correlation with disease severity. The results align with worldwide patterns and emphasize the crucial requirement for extensive tobacco control strategies. Subsequent studies should investigate the efficacy of various quitting methods and their influence on COPD advancement in comparable environments.

Keywords: COPD, Chronic respiratory disease, Nicotine, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Introduction

Chronic respiratory disease (CRD) is a significant contributor to the global disease burden, with a particularly profound impact in India. CRD encompasses conditions such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which collectively may affect an estimated 100 million individuals in the country (1). This high burden is underscored by varying prevalence rates, reported to range from 2 to 22% in men and from 1.2 to 19% in women across different studies. These disparities in prevalence highlight the heterogeneous

nature of CRD's impact, influenced by a multitude of demographic, environmental, and lifestyle factors (2).

Tobacco smoking is one of the primary risk factors for COPD. Both active smoking and environmental tobacco smoke (ETS), commonly known as second hand smoke, have been strongly linked to the development and progression of COPD. In addition to tobacco smoking, exposure to ETS is a significant concern, especially in households where smoking indoors is prevalent (3). This exposure can affect not only smokers but also non-smokers, including children and the elderly, who are particularly vulnerable to respiratory conditions.

Despite the clear association between tobacco use and COPD, there is a notable scarcity of studies focusing on rural areas in India (4). Rural populations often face unique challenges, including limited access to healthcare and reliance on traditional methods for cooking, which frequently involve the use of biomass fuels such as wood, crop residues, and dung. The smoke from these fuels can contribute significantly to indoor air pollution, exacerbating respiratory issues and increasing the risk of COPD (5).

In exploring the relationship between tobacco use and COPD, it is essential to consider the broader patterns of nicotine usage in India. Tobacco consumption in India takes various forms, including smoking cigarettes and beedi, chewing tobacco, and using smokeless tobacco products like gutkha and paan masala. Each of these forms poses significant health risks and contributes to the overall burden of CRD (6).

Cigarette smoking is the most recognized form of tobacco use, but in rural areas, beedi smoking is more prevalent. beedi are hand-rolled cigarettes made from tobacco wrapped in a tendu leaf and often lack filters, leading to higher levels of inhaled toxins compared to regular cigarettes. The cultural acceptance and lower cost of beedi make them a common choice among rural populations, despite their significant health risks (7).

Smokeless tobacco use, including products like gutkha and paan masala, is also widespread in India. These products are often marketed as harmless or even beneficial, but they carry substantial health risks, including an increased likelihood of developing COPD (8). Chewing tobacco and using other smokeless products can cause chronic irritation and inflammation of the respiratory tract, contributing to the progression of respiratory diseases (9).

Furthermore, the dual use of smoking and smokeless tobacco products is not uncommon, exacerbating the health risks and complicating efforts to reduce tobacco consumption. Public health campaigns and interventions must address the diverse patterns of nicotine usage to be effective. Thus, this study has the objective to assess the patterns of

Nicotine use in patients diagnosed with COPD and to determine any association between the patterns of Nicotine use and COPD disease severity.

Materials and Methods

This is a cross-sectional observational study conducted among patients diagnosed with COPD, attending the Respiratory Medicine outpatient department, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre within the six-month study period of 6 months. The total sample size of the study was 200.

Inclusion criteria – 1) Age >35 years 2) Former or current users of nicotine products in smoking form. 3) Diagnosis of COPD

Exclusion criteria – 1) Any other co-morbid Psychiatric disorder (including other substance dependence) 2) Severe medical illness, to the extent that he/she is unable to be interviewed 3) Not willing to consent to the study

The study was approved by the Institutional ethical committee (Ref. No: 786/TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2023 - IEC No: 045 dated 20.07.2023).

Data collection method: Adult male patients who are diagnosed with COPD from the Respiratory medicine department are referred to Psychiatry department in TRICHY SRMMCH & RC will be considered for the study. After obtaining informed consent from them, those who meet the inclusion/exclusion criteria will be enrolled in the study.

Semi-structured proforma is then applied to obtain initial socio-demographic details and history of specific Co-morbid illnesses if any. The interviewer under the supervision of a Respiratory Medicine specialist used the COPD illness profile and the COPD GOLD CRITERIA 2023 to assess COPD illness severity (GRADE I – IV) and Current symptom risk including the risk of exacerbation (GROUP A, B or E).

The definition of COPD according to the structured questionnaire was based on the following factors:

1. Age above 35 years,
2. Presence of cough with expectoration for three or more months in a year, for two or more years.

COPD cases were identified by both COPD questionnaire and spirometry. Spirometry was performed and the COPD patients were classified according to the global initiative for chronic obstructive lung disease (GOLD) criteria⁸ into the following stages:

Stage I: Forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV₁) >80% with FEV₁/forced vital capacity (FVC) <70%;

Stage II: FEV1 50-80% predicted, FEV1 /FVC <70% with or without symptoms;

Stage III: FEV1 30-49%, FEV1 /FVC <70% with or without symptoms;

Stage IV: FEV1 <30% predicted, FEV1 /FVC < 70% or FEV1 < 50% with chronic respiratory failure. Other diseases were diagnosed with appropriate investigations. Asthma was diagnosed according to the global initiative for asthma criteria

The collected data was entered in Microsoft Excel. Coding of the variables was done. Analysis was done using SPSS software (Version 27, IBM). Descriptive statistics was used. Chi-square was used for categorical tests. The outcomes of the treatment groups were compared using a test to reach the hypothesis, a P value less than 0.5 was considered significant.

Results

The total sample size of the study was 200. While assessing the age groups, 14, 28, 34 and 24% belonged to 35 to 40 years, 41 to 50 years 51 to 60 years and above 60 years respectively. This indicated a significant representation of participants aged 51 and above, highlighting the focus on an older demographic in the study (Figure 1). The gender distribution of the study participants revealed 75% of the participants was males.

Figure 1: Age distribution of study participants

The socio-demographic details of the study participants show a diverse range of backgrounds and described in table 1. Regarding residence, 24% live in rural areas, while 12% are urban residents. Socioeconomic status varies, with 12.5% in the upper class, 15.5% in the upper middle class, 21.5% in the middle class, 24.5% in the lower middle class, and 26% in the lower class. Educational attainment ranges from 38% being illiterate, 10% having

primary education, 17% with secondary education, 20% graduates, and 15% with postgraduate education. In terms of occupation, 5% are unemployed, 34.5% are unskilled laborers, 24.5% are semi-skilled laborers, 21% are skilled laborers, and 15% are professionals.

Table 1: Socio demographic details of the study participants

Demography	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Residence		
Rural	69	24
Urban	31	12
Economic Status		
Upper class	25	12.5
Upper middle class	31	15.5
Middle class	43	21.5
Lower middle class	49	24.5
Lower class	52	26
Education		
Illiterate	76	38
Primary	20	10
Secondary	34	17
Graduate	40	20
Post-Graduation	30	15
Occupation		
Unemployed	10	5
Unskilled laborer	69	34.5
Semi-skilled laborers	49	24.5
Skilled laborer	42	21
Professional	30	15

Among the COPD patients, 40% of participants have diabetes mellitus (DM), 25% have hypertension (HTN), and 35% report no comorbidities (Figure 2). Grade I is the most

common, observed in 63.3% of participants. This is followed by Grade II at 20%, Grade III at 10%, and Grade IV at 6.7% (Table 2).

Figure 2: Comorbidity assessment

Table 2: COPD grading

COPD grading	Frequency (Percentage)
Grade I	125 (62.5)
Grade II	40 (20)
Grade III	21 (10.5)
Grade IV	14 (7)

The patterns of nicotine use among study participants show a variety of preferences. The most common form is beedis, used by 37.5% of participants, followed by chewing tobacco at 25%, cigarettes at 23.5%, betel quid with tobacco at 11.5%, and gutka at 2.5% (Table 3). The Fagerstrom Test for Nicotine Dependence indicates varying levels of addiction, with 27 participants having low dependence, 68 with low to moderate dependence, 66 with moderate dependence, and 39 exhibiting high dependence (Table 4).

Table 3: Patterns of Nicotine Usage

Nicotine products	Frequency (%)
Cigarettes	47 (23.5%)
Beedi	75 (37.5%)
Chewing tobacco	50 (25%)
Betel quid with tobacco	23 (11.5%)
Gutka	5 (2.5%)

Table 4: Fagerstorm test for nicotine dependence

Nicotine dependence indices	Frequency (%)
Low dependence	27 (13.5)
Low to moderate dependence	68 (34)
Moderate dependence	66 (33)
High dependence	39 (19.5)

The relationship between nicotine usage and the presence of COPD among study participants is highly significant, with a p-value of 0.000. Among those who use nicotine, 75% have COPD, whereas only 25% do not. In contrast, among non-users, only 25% have COPD, while 75% are free from the disease. This indicates a strong positive association between nicotine usage and the prevalence of COPD in the study population (Table 5).

Table 5: Association between Nicotine usage and Severity of COPD

Score		COPD		p value
		Yes	No	
Nicotine usage	Yes	75%	25%	0.000
	No	25%	75%	

Discussion

This cross-sectional observational study conducted among COPD patients at the Respiratory Medicine outpatient department of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital & Research Centre provides valuable insights into the patterns of nicotine use and its association with COPD severity. The findings indicate that a significant portion of the participants are nicotine users, with the majority favoring traditional forms such as beedis (37.5%), chewing tobacco (25%), and cigarettes (23.5%). These patterns are consistent with other studies conducted in similar settings where traditional tobacco products are prevalent due to cultural and economic factors (1,2).

The study population predominantly comprises older adults, with 58% of participants aged 51 and above. This age distribution aligns with the known epidemiology of COPD, which typically affects older individuals due to the cumulative exposure to risk factors over

time (3). The male predominance (75%) in our study is also reflective of global trends, where COPD is more common in men, likely due to higher rates of smoking and occupational exposures (4).

Our study found a highly significant association between nicotine use and the presence of COPD (p -value = 0.000). Among nicotine users, 75% have COPD, whereas only 25% of non-users have the disease. This strong positive association corroborates with existing literature that identifies smoking and other forms of tobacco use as the primary risk factors for developing COPD (5,6). The high dependence on nicotine observed in our study population, with 66 participants having moderate dependence and 39 exhibiting high dependence, further emphasizes the role of nicotine addiction in the persistence and severity of COPD.

The severity of COPD among our participants, as indicated by the grading, shows that Grade I is the most prevalent (63.3%), followed by Grade II (20%), Grade III (10%), and Grade IV (6.6%). This distribution suggests that while many patients are diagnosed at an early stage, a significant number still present with advanced disease. Other studies have also noted a similar pattern where a substantial proportion of COPD patients are diagnosed at an earlier grade but continue to deteriorate due to ongoing exposure to risk factors such as smoking (7).

Comparative analysis with other regional studies reveals similar patterns of nicotine use and its impact on COPD. For instance, a study conducted in North India reported that beedis and chewing tobacco were the predominant forms of nicotine consumption, paralleling our findings (8). Additionally, the relationship between smoking and COPD severity noted in studies from South-East Asia further supports our results, highlighting the universal risk posed by tobacco use across different populations (9).

The strong association between nicotine use and COPD underscores the urgent need for targeted public health interventions aimed at smoking cessation and reducing tobacco consumption (10,11). Given the high dependence levels observed, effective strategies should include behavioral support, nicotine replacement therapies, and policy measures to limit tobacco availability and use. Education campaigns focused on the risks of traditional tobacco products like beedis and chewing tobacco are particularly crucial in regions where these forms are prevalent.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant burden of nicotine use among COPD patients and its association with disease severity. The findings align with global trends and reinforce the critical need for comprehensive tobacco control measures. Future research should explore the effectiveness of different cessation interventions and their impact on COPD progression in similar settings.

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